

Differentiating Environmental Exposure Effects on Adverse Health Outcomes Near Oil Wells Using Mixture Models

Linyu Zhou¹, Thomas R. Belin¹, Lara Cushing²
Honghu Liu^{1,3}

¹ Department of Biostatistics, Fielding School of Public Health, University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA), Los Angeles, CA, USA

² Department of Environmental Health Sciences, Fielding School of Public Health, UCLA, Los Angeles, CA, USA

³ Public and Population Health, School of Dentistry, University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA), Los Angeles, CA, USA

Abstract

Statistical analysis aimed at assessing the potential impact of oil production on adverse health outcomes near oil wells is challenging. This complexity is due in large part to individuals frequently working away from their residences during regular production hours, which can obscure exposure levels. Our study seeks to navigate these complexities by introducing a Bayesian mixture modeling framework, which effectively characterizes distinct subpopulations based on their varying work patterns. This framework's flexibility is expected to be important in accurately estimating intensity when modeling the spatial point patterns of adverse outcomes within the study area. Utilizing this approach, we seek a deeper understanding of spatial variability and the potential clustering of health outcomes. These outcomes are considered in relation to emissions from oil wells, factoring in both the proximity to and intensity of these wells. Our findings, illustrating the nuanced relationship between oil well emissions and birth outcomes, will be demonstrated through analyses on simulated data.

Key Words: Bayesian Mixture Modeling, Environmental Emissions, Oil Production, Health Outcomes Analysis, Spatial Point Processes

1. Introduction

Oil and gas production plays a crucial role in meeting our energy needs, but it has also raised substantial health concerns, particularly in densely populated areas like Los Angeles. The extraction and processing of fossil fuels release harmful pollutants and greenhouse gasses into air, water, and soil near oil production sites (Johnston et al., 2019).

Over a dozen epidemiological studies conducted near areas with a long history of oil and gas production have examined the relationship between these activities and various adverse health outcomes, including pregnancy complications, cardiovascular and lung issues, and cancer. For instance, a recent scoping review summarized that living near oil and gas production is associated with an increased risk of preterm birth (before 37 weeks of gestation) and reduced fetal growth (Deziel et al., 2020). In California, a statewide analysis found that pregnant individuals living within 1 km of active oil and gas wells producing over 100 barrels of oil equivalent per day had higher odds of adverse fetal growth outcomes, such as low birth weight and small-for-gestational-age births (Tran et al., 2020). Another study in the San Joaquin Valley, CA, reported increased odds of spontaneous preterm birth (delivery before 37 weeks) among those exposed to well sites (Gonzalez et al., 2020). Similar research in rural Colorado and Oklahoma found higher odds of congenital

defects near natural gas development sites (Janitz et al., 2019; McKenzie et al., 2014). In Los Angeles, studies have documented lower lung function and higher blood pressure among residents living near drilling sites, such as those in the Las Cienegas Oil Field (Johnston et al., 2019). Furthermore, childhood hematologic cancers have also been linked to residential proximity to oil and gas development (McKenzie et al., 2017). These findings highlight the health risks associated with oil and gas production, particularly in rural areas; yet in urban environments like Los Angeles, there are very limited studies on the specific health impacts of local, urban-based oil fields.

When modeling disease patterns in environmental studies, it is crucial to consider spatial effects as per Tobler's first law of geography: "everything is related to everything else, but near things are more related than distant things." (Tobler, 1970) Ignoring spatial effects can violate the independent observation assumptions of many statistical models. Tests like Moran's I and Ripley's K are often used to detect spatial autocorrelation or clustering (Moran, 1950; Ripley, 1976). If spatial effects are minimal, standard models may be appropriate; otherwise, models like Generalized Linear Models (GLMs) or Generalized Estimating Equations (GEE) are used to account for spatial similarities within small geographic units, such as census tracts, as seen in previous research (Irena Gorski-Steiner et al., 2022; Rabinowitz et al., 2014; Tran et al., 2020; Whitworth et al., 2017). These models adjust for spatial covariates, enhancing the analysis of disease patterns by incorporating geographic and demographic factors.

When complex spatial patterns are present, modeling disease cases can benefit from using spatial processes to analyze point patterns. Cox Processes are widely used for their ability to handle spatial dependencies in geocoded disease data. Among these, Log-Gaussian Cox Processes (LGCPs) are effective for addressing overdispersion and spatial clustering observed in epidemiological data. LGCPs model the logarithm of the intensity function of the point process as a Gaussian process, directly incorporating spatial correlation into the variability of disease occurrence. This approach captures complex spatial patterns and provides insights into the underlying spatial structure of disease spread. In many health studies, additional information—such as disease severity or patient demographics—is associated with each case and can be treated as marks in the analysis. Marked LGCPs extend the basic LGCP framework by incorporating these marks, allowing for the simultaneous modeling of both the spatial distribution and the attributes of disease events (Ahn et al., 2014; Diggle et al., 2013; Kelling & Haran, 2022; S. Liang et al., 2009). Furthermore, LGCPs can be extended to spatio-temporal settings, enabling the capture of both temporal variations and spatial trends in disease occurrence.

Due to the complex layers inherent in LGCPs, Bayesian hierarchical models are often used, allowing for flexibility in incorporating prior knowledge to explore various aspects of spatial data. Computationally, two commonly used techniques are Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) and Integrated Nested Laplace Approximations (INLA), both are shown to be effectively used for understanding spatiotemporal variations in disease risk (Alexander, 2011; Otiende et al., 2019; Zareie et al., 2023). INLA is known for its computational efficiency, especially in large spatial datasets, because it approximates posterior marginals for parameters in Bayesian inference with lower computational costs and faster processing times compared to MCMC. However, while INLA provides a good approximation, it may sacrifice some accuracy compared to MCMC, which, although computationally slower and more resource-demanding, offers more precise parameter estimates and better captures the full complexity of spatial dependencies. (Gómez-Rubio & Palmí-Perales, 2019; Taylor & Diggle, 2012)

We aim to use a LGCP model to effectively capture the point pattern of disease cases we observed and using INLA to speed up the computation; however, another challenge is the lack of direct measurements of exposure levels. Although numerous studies have been conducted near oil and gas production sites, accurately measuring exposure remains difficult due to various confounding factors. While many studies consider proximity to oil and gas wells as a key factor for exposure, individuals are not continuously exposed because they may work or spend time elsewhere (Adgate et al., 2014). Moreover, pollutants emitted by oil and gas wells—such as carbon monoxide and sulfur dioxide—are confounded with those from other sources like traffic, gasoline, and gas stoves

(Moore et al., 2014). Furthermore, many studies assume constant exposure based on residential proximity, neglecting daily or seasonal variations in production rates or operational changes over time, which could substantially affect actual exposure levels (Paulik et al., 2016). Additionally, individual behaviors—such as time spent indoors versus outdoors—further complicate the accuracy of exposure assessments (Setton et al., 2011).

To address the challenges of unobserved heterogeneity and variability in exposure levels that traditional models struggle to capture, we propose the use of latent variable models—specifically, Bayesian mixture models. These models offer considerable flexibility in modeling complex data structures and can accommodate both observed and latent groupings within populations. They are particularly effective when dealing with unknown mixing components and when prior information is available (Malsiner-Walli et al., 2016; Miller & Harrison, 2018).

In environmental health studies, where unobserved factors frequently affect exposure levels, Bayesian mixture models are invaluable for integrating prior knowledge and managing uncertainties in data analyses (Dunson & Xing, 2012; Molitor et al., 2010; Savitsky & Toth, 2016). For instance, Cucala and Marin (2013) addressed component selection in spatial mixture models by combining Laplace's approximation with innovative techniques to handle the intractability of the normalizing constant in the hidden Potts model, effectively applying this approach to satellite imagery analysis (Cucala & Marin, 2013). Liang et al. (2021) enhanced model flexibility in environmental science by proposing a spatial-functional mixture model for Particulate matter 2.5 (PM_{2.5}) concentrations across China, clustering monitoring stations based on latent emission processes modeled as components of a spatio-temporal process (D. Liang et al., 2021). Similarly, Larsen et al. (2022) utilized a Bayesian framework to estimate the impacts of wildland fires on PM_{2.5} concentrations, employing a causal inference approach to distinguish between fire-contributed and other sources of PM_{2.5} (Larsen et al., 2022).

In summary, our study employs a Bayesian mixture modeling framework to analyze the impact of oil production on adverse health outcomes. This method accounts for the complex exposure variations resulting from individuals' varying work patterns away from home. We simplify the problem by categorizing exposure levels as either high or low, focusing on continuous outcomes for all individuals. We have designed simulation scenarios to evaluate our model's capability in differentiating between these exposure levels. Our results from these simulations, comparing mixture Log-Gaussian Cox Process (LGCP) models with standard LGCP and Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) approaches, demonstrate our model's effectiveness in managing both spatial and non-spatial exposure variations. For the conference submission, we will exclude the analysis of real data, reserving it for a future submission to a peer-reviewed journal.

2. Methods

2.1 Model Description

To capture the influence of multiple underlying processes and spatial effects on disease occurrence, we utilize LGCPs with a mixture structure to account for different exposure levels within the population. Let Z be a binary cluster membership variable representing the exposure status, where $Z = 1$ denotes the high-exposure group and $Z = 0$ denotes the low-exposure group.

The spatial point process \mathbf{X} is defined over an observation window \mathbf{W} , and the intensity function $\Lambda(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{S})$ describes the rate at which points occur in space: here $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is the set of all non-spatial parameters, and \mathbf{S} denotes the set of parameters in the Gaussian processes. By definition of LGCP, condition on $\Lambda(\cdot)$ and \mathbf{Z} , \mathbf{X} follows an inhomogeneous Poisson point process (IHPPP): $\mathbf{X} \mid \Lambda(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{S}), \mathbf{Z} \sim \text{IHPPP}(\Lambda(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{S}))$

The logarithm of the intensity function is modeled as:

$$\log(\Lambda(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{S})) = \mathbf{Z} \cdot \left(\boldsymbol{\beta}_1^T \mathbf{w}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{S}_1(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1, \boldsymbol{\rho}_1) \right) + (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{Z}) \cdot \left(\boldsymbol{\beta}_2^T \mathbf{w}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{S}_2(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\sigma}_2, \boldsymbol{\rho}_2) \right)$$

Here:

- β_1 and β_2 are vectors of regression coefficients for covariates $w(x)$, associated with the high-exposure and low-exposure groups, respectively. $w(x)$ denotes a small area around x .
- $S_1(x; \sigma_1, \rho_1)$ and $S_2(x; \sigma_2, \rho_2)$ are zero-mean Gaussian processes with Matérn covariance functions, capturing spatial dependence within each exposure group.
- $S_1(x)$ and $S_2(x)$ have covariance parameters (σ_1, ρ_1) and (σ_2, ρ_2) , representing the marginal variance and spatial range for each group.

The Gaussian processes $S_1(x)$ and $S_2(x)$ allow the model to account for spatial clustering and overdispersion by incorporating spatial correlation into the variability of disease occurrence. The inclusion of the cluster membership variable Z enables the model to differentiate between high and low exposure levels, providing a more nuanced understanding of how exposure affects spatial patterns.

Prior distributions are specified for the model parameters:

- $\beta_1 \sim N(\mu_{\beta_1}, \sigma_{\beta_1}^2 I_p)$ and $\beta_2 \sim N(\mu_{\beta_2}, \sigma_{\beta_2}^2 I_p)$, where I_p is the identity matrix of dimension p .
- $S_1(x) | (\sigma_1, \rho_1) \sim GP(0, \Sigma_1(x, y; \sigma_1, \rho_1))$ and $S_2(x) | (\sigma_2, \rho_2) \sim GP(0, \Sigma_2(x, y; \sigma_2, \rho_2))$, with Σ_1, Σ_2 representing the covariance functions.
- Hyperparameters (σ_1, ρ_1) and (σ_2, ρ_2) are assumed to have prior distributions from Gamma distributions.

2.2 Simulation Setup

To evaluate the performance of the proposed mixture LGCP model, we conducted simulations designed to compare it with the conventional non-mixture LGCP model. The simulations mimic real-world scenarios where spatial effects and multiple underlying processes, such as environmental exposures, influence the observed data.

We defined the observation window W as a square area of arbitrary units. To simulate point pattern data, we generated realizations from LGCP processes, where the locations of points follow a Poisson process with spatially varying intensity. The log intensity function incorporates both fixed covariate effects and spatial random effects to model the underlying spatial structure.

Specifically, we modeled systolic blood pressure (SBP) among a population, assuming SBP is a continuous variable fully observed without missing data. Individuals at baseline were assigned an average SBP of approximately 120 mmHg. To simulate the effect of environmental exposure, individuals residing closer to a pollutant source—positioned on the western side of W due to a fixed random seed—experienced higher exposure levels, leading to an increased average SBP of around 130 mmHg. This setup creates a spatial gradient in exposure and associated health outcomes, reflecting realistic environmental scenarios.

To replicate high and low exposure groups, we simulated data from a mixture of Gaussian random fields:

- **High-Exposure Group:** Half of the points were simulated with a hotspot on the west side, representing individuals highly affected by the pollutant source.
- **Low-Exposure Group:** The remaining points were generated using another Gaussian random field with lower intensity and variance, featuring a local hotspot on the east side, representing individuals less affected by the pollutant.

Our modeling approach involved several steps:

1. **Simulation of Spatial Points:** We generated spatial point patterns according to the mixture of Gaussian random fields described above, effectively creating two subpopulations with different exposure levels and spatial characteristics.

2. Incorporation of Individual-Level Covariates: Covariates strongly associated with the exposure groups, such as distance from the pollutant source and quadrant membership within W , were included. This reflects realistic scenarios where certain covariates are predictive of exposure and influence the spatial distribution of disease cases.
3. Model Fitting: We fitted the mixture LGCP model using the simulated data, incorporating prior information on high-exposure versus low-exposure groups. The model focused on systolic BP as the continuous mark. It assumed a mean shift in the intercepts (β_1 and β_2) between the two Gaussian random fields but shared other variance parameters. For comparison, we also fitted a standard LGCP model without the mixture structure to assess the advantages of the proposed approach.
4. Model Assessment: To evaluate the performance of the proposed mixture model relative to the standard LGCP model, we calculated the Deviance Information Criterion (DIC) and for each fitted model. Additionally, we conducted predictive checks by comparing the observed data to data simulated from the fitted models, assessing how well each model captures the underlying spatial patterns.

All analyses were conducted using the `R-INLA` (Rue et al., 2009) and `inlabru` packages in R, which are well-suited for fitting both non-spatial and spatial statistical models efficiently.

3. Results

In this study, we generated two simulated spatial fields to model blood pressure levels across a geographic area. The first field, depicted in Figure 1a, represents a higher-exposure environment with an associated elevated blood pressure mean. This field shows a prominent hotspot near the northeast section of the area, where the exposure is assumed to increase blood pressure levels. In contrast, Figure 1b illustrates a second field representing a lower-exposure environment with an overall lower mean blood pressure. This second field features a hotspot on the western side, indicating localized areas of slightly increased values.

The combined distribution of simulated blood pressure values across both fields is shown in Figure 1c. This dual peak pattern confirms the presence of distinct sub-populations within the simulated data, each affected differently by exposure levels.

Figure 1: Overview of simulated data: a) simulated field 1 assuming higher blood pressure because of high exposure; b) simulated field assuming normal blood pressure because of lower exposure level; c) simulated blood pressure for the overall mixture field

To further analyze the spatial patterns, we fit the mean-shift mixture model using the LGCP framework. Posterior mean fields derived from this approach are displayed in Figure 2. Figures 2a and 2b show the spatial patterns predicted by each component of the mixture model. In these figures, spatial variations capture the respective hotspots observed in the simulated fields. For comparison, Figure 2c presents the results from a regular LGCP model. We found our proposed model precisely captured the first mixture component; for the second component, even though the hotspot near the west side was captured, the model also falsely predicted a hotspot in the middle. But overall, we saw that with our mixture model and strong priors on grouping information, it outperforms the regular LGCP model which did not capture the trend in the simulated data.

Moreover, the mixture model achieved a DIC of -772.6177 compared to 12059.77 for the regular model, providing additional quantitative support for its better fit.

Figure 2: Posterior mean field from fitting mixture or regular LGCP models: a) predicted BP from mixture model component 1; b) predicted BP from mixture model component 2; c) predicted BP from regular LGCP.

In terms of computational performance, when attempting to fit the mixture model in MCMC with rjags, it required much longer computational time due to the large number of parameters, taking over two days to complete. By contrast, fitting the model with INLA was much faster, finishing in less than a minute. Supplementary Figure 1 contains detailed MCMC results.

4. Discussion

Understanding the potential health impacts of oil and gas production is critically important, especially for communities located near oil wells. Assessing these impacts poses challenges due to factors such as individuals frequently working away from their residences during production hours, which can obscure true exposure levels. This study demonstrates the capability of our Bayesian mixture modeling framework to accurately capture spatial variations in blood pressure influenced by differing levels of exposure. The mixture model successfully identified distinct spatial patterns associated with higher and lower exposure levels. Specifically, the first field reflecting higher exposure showed an elevated mean with a notable hotspot in the northeast, while the second field with lower exposure displayed a lower overall mean and a hotspot on the western side. These results affirm the utility of our approach in handling heterogeneous spatial data.

We also like to highlight the substantial efficiency of INLA over MCMC. The INLA-based approach not only produced results rapidly but also outperformed the regular LGCP model in terms of capturing spatial heterogeneity when guided by informative priors. This advantage suggests that the mean-shift mixture model, combined with informative priors, is particularly suitable for spatial analyses where computational resources are limited.

However, some limitations should be acknowledged. During the presentation at the Joint Statistical Meetings (JSM), a question was raised regarding the model's ability to address unmeasured confounders, which are prevalent in causal inference studies. While our focus was not on resolving all real-world complexities, we aimed to abstract these issues to enhance statistical methodologies. By simulating exposure-related variations in a controlled setup, we advanced the development of methods that can potentially be adapted for real-world applications, albeit with modifications to handle unmeasured confounders explicitly.

In conclusion, our findings highlight the benefits of the mixture model over regular LGCPs, particularly when informed by strong priors. The model's ability to discern spatial heterogeneity associated with different exposure levels can be a valuable tool in environmental health studies. Ongoing efforts are focused on refining the model by experimenting with alternative priors for the Gaussian process covariance structure to improve robustness. Future work will also explore integrating additional covariates and considering temporal effects to further enhance the model's accuracy and applicability in diverse contexts.

Supplemental Materials

Supplemental Figure 1: Trace plots and posterior density of MCMC model, chain length = 500, $n = 3$.

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